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Health Insurance Demand and Access in Lagos State Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Research has shown that most countries, particularly those in the developing economies of the world have found it almost impracticable to properly finance universal health coverage since only very few countries could provide the meager \$39 to \$40 which is the per capita recommended by the World Health Organization as the annual minimum requirement for basic health care .The primary objectives of this paper are to investigate the access and demand of the health insurance care service in Lagos, Nigeria. A two stage sampling technique was used in the study because sample is taken in two steps. The first step is to select a sample of units, often called primary units, and the second is to select a sample of second stage units or subunits from each chosen primary unit. Our study uses descriptive statistics to throw light on the data before applying multivariate analysis. Multivariate analysis comprises a set of techniques dedicated to the analysis of data sets with more than one variable. We carried out logistic regression and Discriminant analysis to investigate the effect of socio-economic factors on the

demand and access to health insurance. The results showed that income, employment status, service satisfaction and no. of old dependent were the Discriminant parameters in the willingness to buy insurance, with correct assignments. Thus the results suggested that only 4 parameters, i.e., income, employment status, service satisfaction and no. of old dependent were needed to account for most of the expected demand variation in the demand for health insurance by households.

Keywords: Health-Insurance, Demand, Lagos-Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

World Health Organization (2000) in Jutting (2001) observed that health insurance schemes are gradually becoming a recognized tool for financing health care provisions in most economically less developed countries of the world. This argument, he observed was premised on the high demand from people for health services delivery and the possibility of improving access to health care of acceptable quality through insurance. Castro-Leal, et al (2000) in their review of public spending on health care in Africa explained that efficiency and equity are two important policy objectives on which public subsidies for social services are based. According to them, efficiency gains are achieved when such subsidies yield external benefits or correct for market failure. They further explained that health care remains a very important basic service instrument for fighting against poverty. Complementing the aforementioned position, Ron, et al (1990) explained that this is because most conditions that requires medical attention, be they of curative or preventive nature , at any point in the life of an individual would also have financial implications and most people cannot meet the expenses from their limited economic resources. According to them, when the attendant risks and adjacent resources are pooled together among a larger group, the group would be able to pay for the care that each member is likely to require.

In a review of principles guiding the demand for health insurance, Eisenhauer (2006) traced the development of the theory of demand for health Insurance from Arrow (1963) to Nyman (2003). According to him, the position of Arrow(1963) on the issue is rested on the premise that a stronger case would always be made for government provision of insurance as long as private markets for insurance, particularly health insurance is absent, whereas Pauly (1968) argued against national health insurance when he opined that health insurance often induce moral hazards that could culminate in inefficient reallocation of resources and that the institutionalization of such inefficiency through government regulation could consequently reduce welfare. Nyman (2003) took a swipe at Pauly's analysis by arguing that the fundamental belief that risk aversion motivates people to buy insurance is wrong in the first instance. Supporting Arrow's position, Nyman opined that the conventional theory that people buy insurance because of their preference for the certainty of paying small premium to the risk of paying large medical expenses when they finally get sick, becomes justified.

With a population of over 140 million, Nigeria, like many Economically Less Developed Countries (ELCD) realized early enough that there is the urgent need to make health care

affordable and available to its teeming population. This quest to make universal health coverage available to Nigerians led to the setting up of the Halevi Committee by the Nigerian Health Minister in 1962. The report of the Committee was dropped on the floor of Parliament in Lagos due to non-availability of sufficient providers of quality healthcare services (Osuorji, 2006). Tracing the history of NHIS in Nigeria, Adeshina (2009) reported that action on the scheme was resuscitated in 1984 when a committee was commissioned by the Federal Government of Nigeria to study National Health Insurance and in 1988, Professor Olikoye Ransome Kuti, the then Health Minister, commissioned the Eromi Committee on the Establishment of NHIS and its report was finally approved by the Federal Executive Council in 1989. In 1999, the enabling decree No 35 was promulgated and the formal sector of the social health insurance scheme was flagged off in 2005 by the then President of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, Chief Olusegun Obasanjo.

According to Okaro et al (2010), financing of public health services in Nigeria has been through government subvention funded mainly from earnings from petroleum exports and user fees for patents but decline in funding for healthcare commenced after mid 1980's following a drastic reduction in revenue from oil exports, mounting external debts burden, structural adjustment programme and rapid population growth. Quoting Shaw et al (1995), they observed that the result as in most developing countries was a rapid decline in quality and effectiveness of publicly provided healthcare services. Analysing the effectiveness of National Health Schemes, Vogel (1990) listed five criteria. This includes: identifying the beneficiaries, what is the efficiency effects; the equity of financing; administrative costs involvement and political acceptability.

However, research has shown that most countries, particularly those in the developing economies of the world have found it almost impracticable to properly finance universal health coverage. According to Nketiah-Amponsah (2009), health care financing is a big problem in many developing countries and only very few countries could provide the meager \$39 to \$40 which is the per capita recommended by the World Health Organization as the annual minimum requirement for basic health care. Giving the example of Ghana, a country that shares geographical affinity with Nigeria, he opined that low and unstable tax revenues, cutbacks in public budgets and inconsistencies in health policies are some of the factors militating against universal health coverage in that country.

The Nigerian situation is not different from what is obtainable in most African countries. Ogunbekun et al (1999) observed that effective state regulation has resulted in minimal control over the activities of the private sector health providers with the price of health care growing faster than the average rate of inflation. Their study finally suggested that the private sector needed to be fully integrated into the health care reforms.

The Minister of Health of the Federal Republic of Nigeria in an address delivered by him in 2003 captured the limitations in the programme of universal health coverage in Nigeria when he said:

".....I discovered that there was neither a policy framework, nor a practical forum for a dialogue with private health care providers about their potential and actual

contributions to national health goals. Across the African region, the private health sector provides half of all services to patients of all income levels, sometimes in areas where public care is simply not available. Figuring out how to effectively work with the private health sector is therefore a high priority....."

In what looks like an endorsement of the minister's address, the Association of Community Pharmacists in Nigeria (2010) in a release observed that though the universal health coverage scheme in Nigeria was designed with good intention but the implementation had been faulty and fraudulent. In the same document, its National Chairman was quoted to have said that:

"The pharmacists, physiotherapists, laboratory technicians have all been sidelined in the operations of the scheme."

According to him

" A situation in where consultations, prescriptions, laboratory investigations, physiotherapy and dispensing of drugs are carried out by the same person is not in the best interest of the patient. It is unethical and exploitative"

It is in view of these limitations that a paper designed to examine the demand and access to health insurance services in Lagos State Nigeria becomes apt. Apart from the background of the study, the paper has five other sections. Section 2 is on the study area while section 3 discusses the methodology adopted which is followed by presentation of results in section 4. Section 5 examines the policy implications of the study while section 6 is on conclusions and recommendations.

THE STUDY AREA

Lagos State was created on May 27, 1967, through Decree Number 14, by the Federal Government. What was then the Federal Capital of Nigeria was merged with the old colony province of the defunct Western Region of Nigeria to form the new state. The state lies approximately between longitude 2^o42' East and 3^o42' East and latitude 6^o22' North and 6^o52' North. It is bounded in the South by the Guinea Coast of the 180km Atlantic Coastline, in the West by the Republic of Benin and in the North and East by Ogun State (Odumosu, Balogun and Ojo, 1999). The State has twenty local government areas, namely; Agege, Alimosho, Ibeju-Lekki, Surulere, Ojo, Lagos Island, Awori-Ajeromi, Ajeromi-Ifelodun, Shomolu, Epe, Ikorodu, Apapa, Eti-Osa, Badagry, Lagos Mainland, Ikeja, Mushin, Kosofe, Amuwo-Odofin and Ifako-Ijaye.

It has a total area of 3,577 square kilometer about 22 percent of which is water. (Oke *et al.*, 2000). Despite its position as the smallest State in the Federation in terms of land mass, occupying only 0.4 percent of the area of Nigeria, it has gone through series of administrative transformation to metamorphose into a frontline position amongst the thirty-six states making up the federation of modern day Nigeria.

Lagos State with a population of 9,013,534 million, distributed as 4,678,020 males and 4,335,514 females), is the most urbanized state in Nigeria. In 1963, the population of Lagos State was 1,444,000 with 603,000 males and 591,000 females. This grew to 5,725,116 in

1991 with a male population of 3,010,604 and 2,714,512 females. The population density of Lagos State is 2,455. (National Population Commission and National Bureau of Statistics, 2006).

Over 50 percent of industries in Nigeria are located in the state, contributing about 70% of the national gross industrial output. (Oke, et al, 2001). The state accommodates about 6.2 percent of the total population of Nigeria and its annual population growth rate is over 9 percent.

METHODOLOGY

Data

This study employs the sample survey technique. The survey was located in Lagos State, an urban conurbation where the mainstream of the formal sector organizations in Nigeria are situated, since the government's pilot scheme was targeted at the formal sector. The survey that was conducted between September and November 2010 and it involves the collection of information from individual households on accessibility to health insurance scheme. The main instrument of the survey was a structured questionnaire.

A two stage sampling technique was adopted. The major advantage of this sampling method is that it is more flexible than one-stage sampling as it affords the researcher the possibility to take smaller units that produce high efficiency (Cochran, 1977). Lagos has 20 Local Government Areas (LGAs) containing 2,195,842 households (NBS, 2009). A random sample of 4 local government areas were selected for the study and 200 randomly selected households in each local government areas were examined for possession of any kind of health insurance and potential subscription to the NHIS (or any other health insurance). For the purpose of the study, a questionnaire was used to collect data from the heads of households. The questionnaire captured information on the income of the respondents, their age, educational level and employment status in addition to availability of health insurance and willingness to subscribe to one when there is none. The instruments also attempt to capture accessibility and satisfaction of the provider of health care based on the available scheme.

Method

Studies have shown that one of the common statistical tools for investigating household demand for health insurance is multiple regressions (Jiang et al.2003; and Markova, 2006). The present study uses descriptive statistics to highlight the salient features of the data set before applying multivariate analysis. Multivariate analysis comprises a set of techniques dedicated to the analysis of data sets with more than one variable (Abdi, 2003).

Logistic regression and discriminant analysis were conducted to investigate the effect of socio-economic factors on the demand and access to health insurance. Logistic regression describes the relationship between a dichotomous response variable and a set of explanatory variables (see Friendly, 1995; Riley, 2006 and Garson, 2006). In addition to these, discriminant analysis was used to assess the adequacy of classification, given the

group memberships of the objects under study or to assign objects to one of a number of (known) groups of objects. In this study, "Willingness to buy" was taken as the categorical response variables. The objective is to assess the impact of certain socio-economic factors like education, income, labor hours and service satisfaction on willingness to acquire health insurance policy. Thus, these factors are regarded as the explanatory variables.

RESULTS

The average monthly earnings of the household was N124,869.10, though it is as little as N25,000 in some households. The result also shows that the average family size of a household in Lagos State is about 5 people while the mean time spent by households to access their provider is 26.69 and 27.40 minutes from work and home respectively. The average numbers of hours spent by household at work per week is 45.26 hours. The percentage of the household that are self employed, and are willing to buy insurance is 41.9 per cent. Of the households that are not self employed, 55.0 per cent are willing to buy health insurance. Comparatively, the income figures suggests that, for households with income below N50,000, 53.0 per cent are not willing to buy insurance while, 62.8 per cent of the households with income earnings between N100,000 and N200,000 shows the willingness to purchase health insurance.

Multiple Logistic Regression Analysis

Table 1 contains the results from multiple logistic model examining socio-economic characteristics associated with demand in the presence of other variables. The significance of the variables was checked through Wald's statistics. It provides estimates for the odds ratios for each of the independent variables in the model. The odd that a first school leaver will buy a health insurance policy is 0.114246. Similarly, the odd that a holder of Senior Secondary Certificate will buy a health insurance is 0.1381 while that for holders of M.Sc. degree is 0.349673. For household covered by the NHIS, the odd to buy health insurance is 1.315529 while for those without NHIS cover the odd is 0.751232. Households with old people have the odd of 0.752228 of buying health policy and the odd that household whose members are gainfully employed will buy health insurance is 0.362865.

Comparatively, a household in which the head possesses M.Sc. is about 3 times likely to buy health insurance than a household whose head has First School Leaving Certificate. Households with NHIS cover are 1.75 times likely to buy health insurance than household with no NHIS cover. Households that earn income level above N250, 000 are 2.45 times chances of buying health insurance than households with income below N50000.

Table 1 Results from multiple logistic model.

Variables	B	S.E.	Wald	Df	Sig.	Exp(B)
Level of education			1.700754	5	0.888805	
<i>first school leaving certificate</i>	-2.169404	2.272812	0.911074	1	0.33983	0.114246

<i>SSCE</i>	-1.979582	2.112107	0.878447	1	0.348628	0.138127
<i>OND/HND</i>	-0.779985	2.233109	0.121998	1	0.726878	0.458413
<i>B.Sc</i>	-1.532732	1.85852	0.680139	1	0.409539	0.215945
<i>M.Sc</i>	-1.050757	1.685419	0.388677	1	0.532996	0.349673
Labour hour per week	0.0741013	0.026686	7.710553	1	0.00549	1.076916
No. of elderly in household	-0.284317	0.65998	0.185586	1	0.666616	0.752528
Coverage of NHIS			0.346936	2	0.840744	
<i>Everyone</i>	0.2742385	1.06463	0.066353	1	0.796723	1.315529
<i>Nobody</i>	-0.286041	0.857912	0.111166	1	0.738821	0.751232
Employment status(yes)	-1.013724	0.983899	1.061546	1	0.302863	0.362865
Problem with health provider	-0.202768	0.648227	0.097846	1	0.75443	0.816468
Period covered by NHIS in the past 12 months			11.06894	12	0.52302	
<i>1 Month</i>	3.177667	1.582202	4.0336	1	0.044603	23.99072
<i>2 months</i>	3.8212086	1.960722	3.798127	1	0.05131	45.65936
<i>3 months</i>	6.4484679	2.085608	9.559775	1	0.001989	631.7337
<i>4 months</i>	4.4325747	1.91453	5.360282	1	0.0206	84.14779
<i>5 months</i>	4.73967	2.003932	5.594101	1	0.018021	114.3964
<i>6 months</i>	4.0236509	1.800853	4.992107	1	0.025463	55.90484
<i>7 months</i>	2.3957991	1.717349	1.946182	1	0.162999	10.97697
<i>8 months</i>	19.408036	40192.97	2.33E-07	1	0.999615	2.68E+08
<i>9 months</i>	-19.04447	16880.74	1.27E-06	1	0.9991	5.36E-09
<i>10 months</i>	22.51508	40192.97	3.14E-07	1	0.999553	6E+09
<i>11 months</i>	24.495517	28420.72	7.43E-07	1	0.999312	4.35E+10
<i>12 months</i>	3.3865816	1.710984	3.917698	1	0.04778	29.56472
Area of service satisfaction			8.215542	4	0.083994	
<i>efficient & trained physicians</i>	22.921545	20822.79	1.21E-06	1	0.999122	9.01E+09
<i>clean environment</i>	21.559679	20822.79	1.07E-06	1	0.999174	2.31E+09
<i>Availability of drugs</i>	21.65475	20822.79	1.08E-06	1	0.99917	2.54E+09
<i>effective treatment</i>	20.498596	20822.79	9.69E-07	1	0.999215	7.99E+08
Income			8.472913	5	0.132027	
<i>Below 50000</i>	-1.998126	2.095482	0.909239	1	0.340317	0.135589
<i>50000 - 100000</i>	-0.966553	1.894487	0.260297	1	0.609916	0.380392
<i>100000 - 200000</i>	0.3977178	1.805444	0.048527	1	0.825647	1.488424
<i>200000 - 250000</i>	-2.376305	1.843979	1.660706	1	0.197508	0.092893
<i>250000 - 500000</i>	-1.100744	2.273774	0.234357	1	0.628312	0.332624
Constant	-24.33569	20822.79	1.37E-06	1	0.999068	2.7E-11

Discriminant analysis

The demand for health insurance was evaluated using Discriminant Analysis (DA). The objective of DA was to test the significance of discriminant functions and to determine the most significant variables associated with the differences between the clusters.

The statistics shows significant univariate differences in the mean values of the discriminating variables. The direction of these differences is consistent with a priori expectations.

Table 2

Eigenvalues function	R	discriminant function	Wilks' Lambda	Chi-square	dF	p-value
1	0.4532	1	0.7946	24.9503	9	0.0030

Using a stepwise procedure, the process is designed to develop a set of discriminating functions which can help predict demand for health insurance of any household based on the values of other quantitative variables. We develop a model that discriminates among the two levels of Willingness to buy status (or not). The one discriminating function with p-value less than 0.05 is statistically significant at the 95% confidence level. The value of Wilks' lambda and the chi-square for the discriminant function is 0.7946 and 24.9503, and the p-value (0.0030) was below 0.05, indicating that the canonical discriminant function in this study had a greater discriminatory ability of the function and was credible and effective.

The discriminant functions (DFs) and the classification coefficient obtained from the stepwise discriminant analysis are shown in table 3. Using discriminant parameters, the results showed that income, employment status, service satisfaction and number of old dependant were the discriminant parameters in the willingness to buy insurance, with correct assignments. Thus the results suggested that only 4 parameters, i.e., ln income, employment status, service satisfaction and no. of old dependant were needed to account for most of the expected demand variation in the demand for health insurance by households.

Table 3

	Classification Function Coefficients		Fisher's linear discriminant functions
	Yes	No	
Educational level	-8.5597	-8.97268	0.488318

Old dependant	7.262096	6.924534	0.156281
Labour hours/week	0.464082	0.429944	0.466023
NHIS coverage	5.38955	5.245883	0.10595
NHIS coverage period for past 12 months	-0.36062	-0.27948	-0.36881
Employment status	20.08978	19.58693	0.157017
Service satisfaction	9.065085	9.025444	0.019344
Area of service satisfaction	-0.5216	0.144212	-0.73705
Ln Income	25.21646	25.00553	0.188588
(Constant)	-167.86	-162.933	

IMPLICATIONS OF FINDINGS

The implications of these findings are instructive in several respects to policy-makers of the NHIS. The present findings suggest the need for intervention by policy makers if the objectives of the scheme would be actualized. The intervention requires such pragmatic route beyond the traditional boundaries of public health sector. This would include the introduction of tax incentives for those households earning between N100,000 and N200,000 to further boost their willingness to purchase health insurance. Currently, while the legal process of increasing the minimum wage of an average Nigerian worker from N7, 500 to N18,000 is being worked out, the appreciable impact that this would have on the whole population should not be underestimated. This implies that more money would be available to spend on health services. Government should facilitate greater access and demand by developing more health care delivery outlets in the rural areas where most Nigerians are residing. The implication on the health well-being of the nation cannot be overemphasised. Policy makers could leverage on the 'service satisfaction' parameter of this finding by deploying more surveillance on service deliveries of providers through relentless monitoring and supervision. They could set attainable minimum standards that would attract more willing private partnership for greater efficiency of the scheme.

Even more pertinent is the factor of number of the elderly in a household. This factor has the potential of improving the welfare of the aged in the society.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Many societies assume responsibility for the individual health of disadvantaged citizens. People who are old, poor or handicapped would not be able to afford health insurance in a purely private market. Insurance for such people in such a situation should be collectively funded, probably through taxes. Social insurance makes society as a whole to bear the risks of ill health and disability, rather than a defined subgroup delimited by market financial contracts. Many risks that are not capable of coverage with individual or employer policies are thus covered (for example being born with a genetic defect, lack of income, or becoming old).

Social insurance as represented in the NHIS separates the variation in the payments used to finance benefits from variation in the expected cost of benefits, so that the sick and the

well, the young and the old, the healthy and the disabled, all pay the same (although payment may vary with wages, income levels, employment status, service satisfaction and no. of old dependent as shown from results above). This lack of connection between expected payments and expected benefits is both the great strength and the great weakness of the NHIS. Since payments are collective and unrelated to use of services, all sectors of society tend to want to use more medical services and hence, cost control measures must be put in place to check abuse.

In conclusion, for health, more with other lines of insurance, there is public support for using public funds to provide benefits for all. The insurance industry, both private and the NHIS responds with solutions that address the healthcare needs of the society. Access to affordable healthcare is a vital need of any society, and the state is an important financier of the scheme.

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